

SILICON CARBIDE FIBRE REINFORCED NITRIDED
SILICON NITRIDE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Silicon carbide (Nicalon)-fibre reinforced silicon nitride composites were fabricated. Test bars were obtained by slip infiltration of fibre bundles with Si and Si₃N₄ powder and subsequently nitrided in nitrogen at 1350°C for three hours. No reaction was seen between fibre and matrix. Bend tests showed a non-brittle fracture with pull-out and fibre debonding resulting in an increased fracture toughness. Fracture surfaces and polished cross-sections were investigated with SEM.

INTRODUCTION

High performance ceramics such as silicon nitride, silicon carbide, zirconia and alumina are materials with high resistance to wear, corrosion and high temperatures. They have found applications in heat engines, as cutting tool tips and in the aerospace industry. Ceramics are, however, brittle materials with low fracture toughness and probabilistic fracture strength determined by an inherent flaw population. In order to increase the fracture toughness and reliability of ceramics, fibre reinforcement has been successfully employed for some fibre/matrix systems. SiC (whisker) / Al₂O₃ [1], SiC (long fibre) / glass-ceramic [2] and SiC (long fibre) / SiC (chemical vapour infiltration) [3] are materials where an increased fracture toughness and reliability has led to a wider use of ceramics. Silicon nitride is perhaps

the most promising ceramic for high temperature applications, but so far only a few authors report fibre reinforcement of Si₃N₄ [4-7].

The purpose of this study has been to develop an inexpensive fabrication technique, as opposed to chemical vapour infiltration and polymer pyrolysis, for long fibre reinforced Si₃N₄. The studied fibres were Nicalon SiC-fibres. A method involving slip infiltration and reaction sintering was investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fibres

The fibres used were continuous SiC fibres produced by pyrolysis of polycarbosilane. Fibre data are presented below.

Properties of SiC fibres (Nicalon NLM-102, Nippon Carbon Co., Ltd. Japan)

Diameter	15µm
Density	2.55 g/cm ³
Young's modulus	200 GPa
Tensile strength	2500-3000 MPa
Thermal expansion coefficient	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-6}/K^{-1}$

Nicalon fibres were selected after an initial fibre/matrix compatibility study was performed [8, 9].

Matrix

A matrix slurry consisting of a mixture of 55 w/o Si (Sicomill grade II, KemaNord), 37 w/o Si₃N₄ (LC10, HC Starck), 6w/o Y₂O₃ (Dech 570, Rhône Poulenc) and 2 w/o Al₂O₃ (A 16 SG, Alcoa) was prepared by ball milling (Si₃N₄ media) for 90 h in ethanol. This composition is commonly used when preparing nitrided pressurless sintered (NPS) Si₃N₄ [10, 11]. Ytria and

alumina are sintering aids, but they also increase the nitridation rate. The role of Si_3N_4 is that of a dispersant to enable the Si to reach submicron size during milling, to prevent sintering of Si during nitridation by keeping the Si particles apart, and by acting as a heat sink during the exothermal nitridation reaction. These additions result in a very short nitridation time (3-4 h) as compared with reaction bonding of pure Si powder compacts.

Slip Infiltration

A matrix slip was prepared from the milled powder, ethanol and 5 % polyethyleneimine, by powder weight, as dispersant and binder. Fibre bundles cut in 5 cm lengths were dipped in the matrix slurry and stacked in a mould, according to figure 1, to form bars. The cast test bars were dried carefully first at room temperature and then at 100°C .

Figure 1. Slip casting mould.

Nitridation

The slip infiltrated test bars were nitrided in a graphite resistance furnace in N_2 at atmospheric pressure. A two-step temperature program was used where the temperature was first held at 1200°C for 0.5 h and then raised to 1350°C for 3 h.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

At this stage no attempts have been made to optimize the fibre distribution to get a homogeneous microstructure. The first step was to see if fibre bundles could be sufficiently infiltrated by matrix slip. As can be seen in figure 2 the infiltration of matrix material between the fibres is fairly good. A way to get a more homogeneous microstructure would be to use a fibre preform and infiltrate with matrix slip.

Figure 2. Backscattered electron image of a cross-section of a nitrated composite (black = porosity) (bar = 100 μm).

Fibre/Matrix Compatibility

Earlier investigation of SiC (Nicalon) fibre reinforced reaction bonded Si₃N₄ [7] indicated a reaction between fibre and matrix. This was not observed in the present investigation. The reason for this might be the much shorter nitridation time (3-4 h as compared to 5 days). In figure 3b the smooth surface of a pulled out fibre can be seen.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of a fracture surface of a nitrided composite. B. Close-up of fibre (bar = A:100 μm , B:10 μm).

Fracture Behaviour

As can be seen on the fracture surface in figure 3a mechanisms such as fibre debonding and fibre pull-out seem to operate thus increasing the fracture toughness. The load/displacement curve in figure 4 shows a non-brittle fracture behaviour with high fracture energy (proportional to the area below the curve). Further development of the slip infiltration step to yield a more homogeneous microstructure should lead to increases in strength and toughness.

Figure 4. Load/displacement curve for a nitrided composite.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that slip infiltration of fibre bundles, can be used as a forming method for ceramic-ceramic composites. Nitridation of Si/Si₃N₄ mixtures yields a good matrix with no reaction with the Nicalon fibres. When, in the future, the high temperature resistance of ceramic fibres is increased the nitrided composites can be hot isostatically pressed or pressureless sintered to a higher density but even the nitrided material shows promising mechanical properties which may be sufficient for some applications.

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